

RENEWAL PROCESSES IN THE MEDIA SPACE AND URGENT TASKS OF EDUCATING THE THREATENED GENERATION

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Abstract. According to the Uzbek scientist B. Umarov, “the end of 20th century – the 21st the new global formed in the world development at the beginning of the century, the essence of the civilization stage, the complexity and expansion of relations between states and people, the information space around the world, all spheres of society’s life – economy, politics, ideology, culture, even personal is connected with the process of globalization covering the way of life.” This, in turn, is carried out by the processes in the media space. The rise of threats through new platforms, programs, technologies is leading to changes in the political and social system. The sociocultural changes formed by the introduction of digital media technologies and media communication practices into the everyday life of young people become apparent. Through this article, we will analyze them and consider the importance and tasks of educating youth who are resilient to threats.

Keywords: media space, generation, resistance, threats, misinformation, communication.

Аннотация. По мнению узбекского учёного Б.Умарова, «конец 20-го века – XXI век – новый глобальный, сформировавшийся в мировом развитии в начале века, суть цивилизационного этапа, усложнение и расширение отношений между государствами и людьми». Информационное пространство во всем мире, все сферы жизни общества – экономика, политика, идеология, культура, даже личная – связаны с процессом глобализации, охватывающим образ жизни». Это, в свою очередь, осуществляется процессами в медиaprостранстве. Рост угроз через новые платформы, программы, технологии приводит к изменениям в политической и социальной системе. Становятся очевидными социокультурные изменения, вызванные внедрением цифровых медиатехнологий и практик медиакommunikаций в повседневную жизнь молодежи. В этой статье мы проанализируем их и рассмотрим важность и задачи воспитания молодежи, устойчивой к угрозам.

Ключевые слова: пространство медиа, поколение, сопротивление, угрозы, дезинформация, коммуникация.

Annotatsiya. O‘zbek olimi B.Umarovning yozishicha, “XX asrning oxiri –XXI asrning boshida jahon taraqqiyotida shakllangan yangi umumsayyoraviy tartib, tamadduniy bosqich mazmun-mohiyati, davlatlar va kishilar o‘rtasidagi o‘zaro aloqalarning murakkablashishi va kengayishi, dunyo bo‘yicha axborot makoni jamiyat hayotining barcha sohalari – iqtisodiyot, siyosat, mafkura, madaniyat, hatto shaxsiy turmush tarzini qamrab olgan globallashuv jarayoni bilan bog‘lanmoqda.” Bu esa o‘z navbatida media-makondagi jarayonlar bilan amalga oshiriladi. Yangi platformalar, dasturlar, texnologiyalar orqali tahdidlarning avj olishi siyosiy va ijtimoiy tizimdagi o‘zgarishlarga olib kelyapti. Yoshlarning kundalik hayotiga raqamli media-texnologiyalar va media-kommunikatsiya amaliyotlarini joriy etish natijasida shakllangan ijtimoiy-madaniy o‘zgarishlar yaqqol namoyon bo‘lmoqda. Biz ushbu maqola orqali ularni tahlil qilamiz va tahdidlarga bardoshli yoshlarni tarbiyalashning ahamiyati va vazifalarini ko‘rib chiqamiz.

Kalit so‘zlar: media makon, avlod, qarshilik, tahdid, axborot xuruji, kommunikatsiya.

In today’s fast-paced digital age, the media landscape is constantly evolving. As new technologies and platforms emerge the way we consume and interact with media is changing rapidly. To adapt these changes and ensure a resilient future, media practitioners are embracing updates to their processes while striving to raise a generation that is resistant to the threats prevalent in the modern media space. One of the first steps in updating processes in the media space involves leveraging technology to combat misinformation and disinformation. With the proliferation of fake news and misleading content, media organizations are focusing on implementing fact-checking mechanisms and automated tools to verify the authenticity of information before it is disseminated. By doing so, they aim to promote accuracy and integrity in all forms of media.

Media is undergoing significant changes today due to various factors, including technological advancements, shifts in audience behavior and evolving business models. Here are some ways in which the media landscape is changing:

1. Digital transformation: Traditional media outlets are increasingly embracing digital platforms to reach wider audiences and adapt to changing consumption patterns. This includes the transition from print to online newspapers, the expansion of digital streaming services and the proliferation of podcasts and digital magazines.

2. Social media platforms have become influential players in the media landscape, shaping public discourse and serving as primary sources of news and information for many people. Media organizations are leveraging social media to engage with audiences, distribute content and gather feedback in real-time.

3. Content diversification: Media outlets are diversifying their content offerings to cater to diverse audience interests and preferences. This includes the production of multimedia content, interactive experiences and niche content targeting specific demographics or communities.

4. Data-driven insights: Media organizations are increasingly utilizing data analytics and audience insights to understand consumer behavior, tailor content recommendations and optimize advertising strategies. Data-driven decision-making is becoming essential for staying competitive in the media industry.

Advancements in technologies such as artificial intelligence, virtual reality and augmented reality are reshaping the media landscape by enabling new forms of storytelling, immersive experiences and personalized content delivery. The media landscape is evolving rapidly, driven by technological innovation, changing consumer preferences and market dynamics.

In our country, Y. Mamatova, S.Sulaymonova (2015 y), N.Qosimova, A. Dadaxonov (2019 y) are working on the issue of studying the consumption of the media environment of the older and younger generation.

The younger generation is a subject for discussion of different points of view, due to the fact that the beginning of its life and transition to adulthood took place in the digital age, which is the main indicator for this generation.

But today these numbers change again. Nevertheless, people born in the 2000s differ in many serious characteristics of media consumption both from other generations and from the general population. They waste time just watching videos. Watching too many videos, especially for

extended periods, can have several negative effects on individuals’ physical, mental and social well-being.

While media can offer numerous benefits to children's education, there are also potential dangers and drawbacks to consider: Not all content available in the media is accurate or reliable. Children may be exposed to misinformation, inaccuracies, or biased perspectives, which can distort their understanding of reality and negatively impact their education. Children may inadvertently encounter inappropriate or harmful content, such as violence, explicit language, or adult themes, while using media platforms. Exposure to such content can be distressing for children and may have adverse effects on their emotional well-being and development. Excessive screen time and passive media consumption can interfere with children's cognitive development, attention span, and ability to focus. Research suggests that prolonged exposure to screens may have detrimental effects on brain development, particularly in young children.

Heavy media use, especially of entertainment media, has been associated with negative social and behavioral outcomes in children, such as decreased social interaction, impaired social skills, and increased aggression. Children are often targeted by advertisers through media platforms, promoting products and consumerism. Exposure to advertising can influence children's preferences, values, and behaviors, leading to excessive materialism and unhealthy consumption habits. Media portrayals of gender, race, and other social identities can reinforce stereotypes and biases, shaping children's attitudes and perceptions. Limited or inaccurate representation in media can contribute to feelings of exclusion, discrimination, and low self-esteem among marginalized groups. Children may face risks such as cyberbullying, online harassment, and exposure to inappropriate interactions or predators while using digital media platforms. Lack of supervision and guidance can make children vulnerable to online threats and compromise their safety. Excessive use of digital media, particularly interactive and addictive content such as video games and social media, can lead to problematic behaviors and addiction-like symptoms, affecting children's overall well-being, academic performance, and social relationships.

To mitigate these dangers, it's essential for parents, caregivers, educators, and policymakers to promote media literacy, supervise children’s media use, select age-appropriate content, and establish healthy screen-time limits. Additionally, fostering open communication with children about media consumption and teaching critical thinking skills can empower them to navigate the media landscape safely and responsibly.

On the issue of youth education, it is a matter of general concern for nearly all countries. Regarding the topic of youth education, President Sh. Mirziyoyev of the Republic of Uzbekistan stated the following at the 72nd session of the United Nations General Assembly: “Today's youth are the largest generation in human history, as they constitute 2 billion people. As we celebrate World Children’s Day, the future of our prosperity depends on how well our children mature into responsible adults. Our main task is to create the necessary conditions for young people to realize their potential and to combat the “virus” of extremism. Therefore, we consider it necessary to further develop comprehensive cooperation in promoting social support for youth, protecting their rights and interests.

In this regard, Uzbekistan proposes to develop a comprehensive international legal document, the United Nations Convention on the Rights of Youth, to shape and implement policies related to youth and to protect and promote their interests.

In our view, the states that will sign this document should take upon themselves the absolute responsibility to elevate their social policy to a fundamentally important and vital level in this area.”

Therefore, in such an intense period, it is necessary for us to prepare our children to be resilient and responsive to all sorts of media influences and to have media literacy. To prepare our children to be resilient and responsive to various media influences and to enhance their media literacy, we can take several actions:

Educate Them: Provide children with education on media literacy, teaching them critical thinking skills to analyze and evaluate media messages critically. Help them understand the techniques used in media, such as advertising strategies and biases.

Monitor Their Media Consumption: Supervise and monitor the media content children consume, ensuring it is age-appropriate and aligns with family values. Encourage discussions about media content and its potential impact on beliefs and behaviors.

Promote Healthy Media Habits: Set limits on screen time and encourage balanced media consumption with other activities such as outdoor play, reading, and socializing. Model healthy media habits by demonstrating responsible screen use yourself.

Encourage Questioning and Discussion: Encourage children to question the information they encounter in media and engage in discussions about different perspectives and interpretations. Foster open communication where children feel comfortable expressing their opinions and asking questions.

Teach Online Safety: Educate children about online safety practices, including protecting personal information, recognizing and reporting cyberbullying, and avoiding interactions with strangers online.

Provide Positive Media Alternatives: Offer children access to high-quality, educational media content that promotes positive values, diversity, and creativity. Explore various media formats such as books, documentaries, podcasts, and educational apps.

Lead by Example: Be a positive role model for responsible media use by demonstrating critical thinking skills, healthy media habits, and digital etiquette. Engage in joint media experiences and discussions with your children to model positive media behavior.

Stay Informed and Involved: Stay informed about current media trends, issues, and developments, and stay involved in your children's media experiences. Advocate for media literacy education in schools and communities and support initiatives that promote positive media environments for children.

By taking these proactive steps, we can empower our children to navigate the media landscape confidently, critically evaluate media content, and make informed choices about their media consumption.

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